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Confluence of Research, Theory and Practice in the
Built Environment

EDITORS

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EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL OF VIRTUAL REALITY IN REVOLUTIONIZING FACILITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN THE NIGERIAN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

The construction industry is rapidly evolving with the integration of Industry 4.0 technologies, particularly virtual reality (VR), which has the potential to revolutionise facility management. However, limited research exists on specific areas where VR can be applied to enhance facility management practices in Nigeria. This study investigates key VR applications within the Nigerian construction industry. A literature review informed the development of a structured questionnaire, distributed to construction professionals. Data analysed using SPSS identified five key areas for VR application: collaboration and communication, sustainability and green building, asset management, emergency planning, and space planning and design. Factor analysis grouped these into three categories: strategic facility optimisation, sustainable experience management, and critical response and training solutions. The findings reveal that VR can enhance project visualisation, communication, and decision-making, providing companies with a competitive edge. Integrating VR can improve efficiency and quality in design and management processes. The study concludes that incorporating VR into the Nigerian construction industry will not only enhance workforce skills but also position the sector as a leader in innovative technologies, attracting international investment and fostering collaboration.

Keywords: Virtual Reality (VR), Facility Management (FM), Innovation, Sustainable Cities, Construction Industry

INTRODUCTION

Facility management plays a vital role in the construction sector, encompassing maintenance, operations, and infrastructure optimisation to support efficient and profitable operations (Xiong *et al.*, 2024). In the current technological landscape, effective facility management increasingly relies on digital innovations like virtual reality (VR) to improve resource efficiency, reduce costs, and ensure project continuity (Hou *et al.*, 2024). Traditional facility management methods often lead to inefficiencies and decision-making constraints, despite their significant influence on building costs. Efficient management throughout a project's lifecycle is essential,

with stakeholders overseeing critical activities such as quantity takeoff, cost estimation, and procurement (Hakimi *et al.*, 2024).

Emerging technologies like VR are being adopted by construction stakeholders to address the limitations of traditional 2D methods and streamline facility management processes (Ghansah, 2024). VR enhances facility management capabilities by providing immersive, interactive virtual environments (Hsiao *et al.*, 2024). These high-fidelity simulations enable better planning and decision-making by integrating digital models into three-dimensional solutions (Miller *et al.*, 2024). VR's advanced interfaces allow stakeholders to simulate maintenance scenarios, optimise preventive maintenance, assess costs, and visualise complex data sets, leading to reduced downtime and improved efficiency (Durmus and Gunaydun, 2024).

Although VR has been successfully integrated into various industries, its adoption in construction, especially in facility management, remains limited. Previous research has explored VR applications in areas like construction project management (Albahbah *et al.*, 2021) and factors influencing VR adoption in the UK (Delgado *et al.*, 2020). Other studies, such as those by Odili *et al.*, (2024) and Ribeiro *et al.*, (2024), have focused on challenges in technology adoption in Nigeria and the readiness for Industry 4.0 technologies in Brazil. Furthermore, Bao *et al.*, (2024) discussed VR's potential within a token incentive framework. Despite these valuable insights, there is still a gap in comprehensively exploring VR's potential in facility management. This study addresses this gap by investigating the specific areas within facility management in Nigeria where VR can enhance efficiency, safety, and cost-effectiveness. By focusing on developing countries like Nigeria, the research provides fresh insights and practical recommendations for leveraging VR technology. This study not only contributes to the advancement of facility management practices but also supports broader technological adoption in similar regions, promoting global trends in VR integration. Thus, this study provides the first in-depth exploration of VR's potential in facility management in Nigeria's construction industry, offering innovative solutions that can enhance efficiency and attract international investment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Facility Management in the Construction Industry

Facility management (FM) originated within the fields of architecture, engineering, and real estate, with an initial focus on the maintenance of physical spaces. As organisations grew, the role of FM expanded to encompass strategic planning and support for essential business operations (Durmus and Gunaydun, 2024). FM ensures the efficient use, maintenance, and operation of built environments throughout their lifecycle, concentrating on space optimisation, energy efficiency, and user satisfaction. This enhances asset longevity and reduces operational costs (Ghansah, 2024). Under stable economic conditions, FM plays a critical role in aligning buildings, systems, and services with core organisational goals (Xiong *et al.*, 2024). It covers various aspects such as computerisation, inventory management, life cycle costing, property asset management, and post-occupancy evaluations (Zhi and Husain, 2024). The scope of FM spans multiple areas, including janitorial services, mechanical and electrical systems, building structures, and security, among others (Odilli *et al.*, 2024).

Virtual Reality Technology in the Construction Industry

Virtual reality (VR) involves using computer technology to generate immersive visual, auditory, and sensory experiences (van Wyk *et al.*, 2024). Since its development in the 1990s, VR has gained prominence across multiple sectors, including construction, engineering,

architecture, and medicine (Durmus and Gunaydun, 2024). VR allows users to interact with a computer-generated 3D environment, typically through headsets and motion-tracking devices, providing a sense of immersion (Miller *et al.*, 2024). The goal of VR is to offer users a realistic experience where they can engage with objects and navigate virtual spaces, enhancing interaction and spatial awareness (Odilli *et al.*, 2024; Hou *et al.*, 2024).

Virtual Reality in Facility Management

Virtual reality is reshaping facility management by offering innovative solutions to traditional challenges (Hou *et al.*, 2024). VR enables enhanced interaction with building systems and equipment, allowing facility managers to conduct realistic assessments of maintenance needs and user experiences (Miller *et al.*, 2024). By bridging the gap between design, construction, and facility operations, VR improves spatial visualisation, communication, and simulation, empowering stakeholders throughout the process (Hakimi *et al.*, 2024). It also helps facility managers optimise layouts, accessibility, and user experiences by simulating spaces from the occupants' perspective, which is especially useful in sectors like hospitality and retail (Hsiao *et al.*, 2024).

Applications of Virtual Reality in Facility Management

VR has proven to significantly enhance efficiency, training, and visualisation in facility management. It assists in planning and space visualisation, helping facility managers identify potential issues before physical modifications occur (Joy and Raja, 2024). Moreover, VR can be used to train employees on safety protocols, emergency responses, and equipment operations in a controlled environment, thereby reducing downtime and errors (Scorgie *et al.*, 2024; Johansson and Roupé, 2024). In asset management, VR aids in tracking asset locations and planning for their maintenance or replacement (Xiong *et al.*, 2024). It also simulates energy usage, supporting energy optimisation and the implementation of sustainable measures (Hou *et al.*, 2024). For emergency planning, VR offers realistic disaster simulations, allowing facility managers to refine their response strategies (Hakimi *et al.*, 2024). Large facilities benefit from virtual tours and navigation tools, which assist both staff and visitors (Miller *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, VR allows stakeholders to visualise improvements before they are implemented, improving decision-making and reducing the risk of costly errors during construction (Li and Li, 2024). Facility managers can also gather feedback on space designs via VR, ensuring that layouts meet user requirements (Artan *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, VR supports remote management, enabling virtual inspections and assessments of multiple sites (Ghansah, 2024). It enhances communication and collaboration among stakeholders by providing a shared virtual space for resolving issues (Durmuş and Günaydın, 2024). Lastly, VR can model the environmental impacts of buildings, aiding in the adoption of sustainable practices and the achievement of green certifications (Shoaib *et al.*, 2024). In summary, VR offers significant potential to revolutionise facility management by enhancing efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and sustainability across a range of applications.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a quantitative research design to explore potential applications of virtual reality (VR) in facility management (Haq, 2015). Data was collected through a structured questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale, where 5 represents 'strongly agree' and 1 represents 'strongly disagree'. This scale allows the quantification of respondents' attitudes and perceptions, facilitating detailed analysis of VR adoption in facility management (Weber *et al.*,

2014). The study targeted professionals involved in facility management within the construction industry, including architects, quantity surveyors, builders, and engineers, key stakeholders in optimizing building performance and infrastructure management. The research was conducted in Lagos and Abuja, Nigeria's major commercial and administrative centres (Wahab *et al.*, 2020). Lagos, a hub of rapid urbanization and construction activity, was ideal for studying emerging technologies such as VR. Meanwhile, Abuja, as the nation's capital, offered insights into facility management in both public and private sectors.

The sample included professionals actively engaged in facility management, familiar with VR technology, and willing to participate. The sampling frame was developed from professional bodies, construction companies, and other relevant organizations. Sample size was determined using Yamane's (1967) formula, with 137 questionnaires distributed. A total of 108 were returned, yielding a response rate of 78.8%. Convenience sampling was employed for practical reasons, such as ease of access and data collection. While convenience sampling may introduce some bias due to the lack of randomization (Scholtz, 2021), it was deemed suitable given the time constraints, resource limitations, and the need for prompt insights from a specialised group of professionals (Sexton, 2022).

To mitigate bias, efforts were made to include participants from diverse organizations and regions, ensuring broader representation and increasing the validity of the study. The questionnaire consisted of two sections: Section A collected demographic data, while Section B focused on identifying areas where VR can be integrated into facility management. The questionnaires were self-administered and distributed electronically via Google Forms, which helped maximize the response rate and ensure a wide range of responses. Data analysis involved statistical methods such as frequency distribution, percentages, mean item score, standard deviation, and factor analysis. Frequency distribution and percentages were used to analyze respondents' demographic data. The mean item score provided a measure of central tendency for each question (Naomg, 2010), while standard deviation indicated the variability in respondents' perceptions (Delmas & Liu, 2005). Factor analysis was employed to identify underlying relationships among variables, grouping related items to simplify data interpretation (Brown & Moore, 2012). The reliability of the instrument was confirmed with a Cronbach's alpha score of 0.943, indicating a high level of internal consistency (Kimberlin & Winterstein, 2008). By utilizing these methodologies, this study offers a comprehensive analysis of the potential applications of VR in facility management, contributing to both academic knowledge and practical insights for construction industry stakeholders.

RESULTS

Respondents' Demographics

Table 1 provides a detailed breakdown of the data collected from the retrieved questionnaires, focusing on the demographic characteristics of the professionals surveyed. Architects represented the largest group, accounting for 28.7% of respondents, followed by quantity surveyors at 26.9%, engineers at 25%, and builders at 19.4%. The table also includes an analysis of respondents' academic qualifications, years of professional experience, and membership in professional organizations.

Table 1: Respondent’s Demographics

Category of the Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Academic Qualification of Respondents		
(HND) Higher national diploma	26	24.1
(B/Tech/BSc) Bachelor’s degree	35	32.4
(M/Tech/MSc) Master’s degree	31	38.7
(PhD) Doctor of philosophy	16	14.8
Total	108	100
Profession of respondents		
Architect	31	28.7
Engineers	27	25
Builders	21	19.4
Quantity Surveyor	29	26.9
Total	108	100
Years of experience		
1-5 years	37	34.3
6-10 years	23	21.3
10-15 years	11	10.20
16-20 years	28	25.90
Above 21 years	9	8.3
Total	108	100
Membership status		
Probationer	10	9.3
Graduate	21	19.4
Cooperate	33	30.6
Fellow	44	40.7
Total	108	100

Areas where Virtual Reality can be applied in Facility Management

Mean score

Table 2 outlines the top five areas where virtual reality (VR) is most commonly applied in facility management. The highest-rated application area is collaboration and communication, with a mean score of 4.85. This is followed by sustainability and green building (mean = 4.72), asset management (mean = 4.49), emergency planning (mean = 4.34), and space planning and design (mean = 4.31).

Table 2: The Analysis of the Mean Item Score of the Areas

Areas	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
Collaboration and communication	4.85	0.53	1
Sustainability and green building	4.72	0.56	2
Asset management	4.49	0.58	3
Emergency Planning	4.34	0.60	4
Space planning and design	4.31	0.65	5
Training and Simulation	4.25	0.66	6
Maintenance and Repairs	4.19	0.69	7
Energy management	4.17	0.72	8
Occupant experience	4.08	0.73	9
Renovation planning	4.07	0.77	10
Remote management	3.50	2.87	11
Wayfinding and Navigation	3.47	2.89	12

Factor Analysis

Table 3 presents the results of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity, which assess the suitability of the data for factor analysis. The KMO value of 0.776 indicates that 77.6% of the data are adequate for factor analysis, suggesting a high level of sampling adequacy. Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity confirms the appropriateness of the data for analysis, with a p-value of less than 0.05, a degree of freedom of 66, and an approximate chi-square value of 5353.684. The highly significant p-value (p = 0.000) further indicates that the correlation matrix of the variables shows a strong correlation at the 5% significance level, making exploratory factor analysis suitable for this study.

Table 3: Analysis of the Factor Analysis

KMO measure of sampling adequacy		0.776
Barlett’s test of sphericity	Approximate chi-square	5353.684
	Df	355
	Sig	0.000

Areas where Virtual Reality can be Applied

	1	2	3	4
Cluster1: Strategic Facility Optimization				
Space planning and design	0.874	–	–	–
Maintenance and repairs	0.826	–	–	–
Renovation planning	0.794	–	–	–
Asset management	0.634	–	–	–
Cluster 2: Sustainable Experience Management				
Sustainability and green buildings	–	0.898	–	–
Energy management	–	0.738	–	–
Occupant experience	–	0.702	–	–
Wayfinding and Navigation	–	0.618	–	–
Cluster 3: Critical Response and Training Solution				
Collaboration and communication	–	–	0.756	–
Emergency planning	–	–	0.743	–
Training and simulation	–	–	0.734	–
Remote management	–	–	0.601	–

DISCUSSION

Cluster One: Strategic Facility Optimisation

This cluster stands out as the most significant, with the highest average mean value for its variables. This section underscores how virtual reality (VR) is transforming facilities management by allowing managers to visualize and optimize layouts before construction. The ability to model potential issues early facilitates proactive maintenance, and the use of immersive platforms enhances asset tracking, reducing errors and improving strategic management. This aligns with findings by Joy and Raja (2024) and Scorgie *et al.*, (2024), which highlight the role of VR in increasing both efficacy and efficiency in facilities management. Additionally, VR provides a comprehensive overview of changes, improving the accuracy of remodeling planning and reducing errors (Li & Li, 2024). It also centralizes asset management through an immersive platform, allowing managers to efficiently track and manage building components.

The Second Cluster: Sustainable Experience Management

This cluster focuses on the growing importance of sustainability and occupant experience in facility management. VR supports these efforts by enabling the simulation of green building options and energy management improvements. Shoaib *et al.*, (2024) and Hou *et al.*, (2024) reinforce these points by demonstrating how VR contributes to better energy efficiency. Additionally, VR promotes a more sustainable and user-centered approach to facility management. VR enhances the occupant experience by creating interactive spaces that meet user needs and increase productivity (Artan *et al.*, 2024).

The Third Cluster: Critical Response and Training Solutions

This cluster addresses emergency preparedness and training in facilities management. The ability of VR to simulate disaster scenarios and provide interactive training greatly improves response planning and employee preparedness, as noted by (Durmuş and Günaydın, 2024) and (Ghansah, 2024). Furthermore, VR facilitates global collaboration and remote management, offering a more flexible and responsive approach to managing facilities. Additionally, VR allows facilities to be supervised and controlled from any location (Ghansah, 2024). Overall, these VR applications enhance facility management teams' readiness and resilience, ensuring a safer and more robust building environment.

IMPLICATION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study hold substantial implications for researchers, facility managers, and construction stakeholders. They provide a structured framework for exploring facility management strategies and guide future research to fill existing knowledge gaps. By focusing on these factors, researchers can further investigate how virtual reality (VR) technology enhances sustainability, optimises space design, and improves asset management, ultimately leading to more efficient facility operations. For facility managers, VR offers tangible benefits such as the ability to visualise and design spaces, simulate maintenance procedures, and model energy usage.

These capabilities directly address challenges related to space optimisation, maintenance efficiency, and energy consumption, thereby reducing costs and improving operational performance. Nigerian construction stakeholders including engineers, architects, and project managers—can also leverage VR to enhance decision-making. VR facilitates the simulation of emergency responses, the collection of resident feedback, and the planning of renovations, enabling stakeholders to meet needs while minimising risks and errors. Overall, these findings highlight how VR can drive innovation and improve project outcomes within the construction sector. By integrating VR technologies, the industry can address critical issues such as efficiency, sustainability, and collaboration, leading to more advanced and effective construction practices.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study evaluates the application of Virtual Reality (VR) technology in facility management within the Nigerian construction industry. Using a quantitative research approach, tools such as frequency distribution, percentages, mean item score, and factor analysis identified key areas where VR is most effective. The findings reveal that collaboration and communication,

sustainability and green building, asset management, emergency planning, and space planning and design are the top areas of VR application. These twelve identified areas were consolidated into three component factors: Strategic Facility Optimisation, Sustainable Experience Management, and Critical Response and Training Solutions. Among these, Strategic Facility Optimisation stands out as the most significant, with the highest average mean for its variables, highlighting its critical role in enhancing space planning, asset tracking, and overall facility efficiency.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that facility managers and construction stakeholders in Nigeria incorporate VR into their workflows to enhance space planning, asset management, and sustainability efforts. Researchers should further explore the potential of VR to optimise facility operations and address industry challenges. The construction industry should prioritise VR adoption to improve decision-making, reduce costs, and enhance project collaboration. Future research should also focus on investigating the long-term impact of VR on facility management efficiency, particularly in terms of cost savings and sustainability outcomes. Additionally, exploring the integration of VR with emerging technologies, such as Building Information Modelling (BIM), could offer further optimisation of construction and facility management processes.

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